

ENSURING COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT IN AIRBORNE WIND ENERGY (AWE) PROJECTS

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ABOUT

Wind Lab 3 is about co-producing, testing and promoting participatory practices for airborne wind energy (AWE). As more AWE projects are being implemented, it is important for the sector to ensure a high level of social acceptance from the very beginning.

KEY TOPICS

- Applying best practices of community engagement to the nascent Airborne Wind Energy (AWE) sector
- Ensuring that AWE project developers are well aware of the importance of local social acceptance
- Understanding the specific challenges of AWE, notably the lack of widespread experience about the technology

GUIDELINES

TREAT COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT LIKE PERMITTING OR ENGINEERING—IT'S A CORE PROJECT DISCIPLINE

Budget for staff time, events, consultants, and communications, even if this may be challenging for AWE companies.

ENGAGE EARLY WITH COMMUNITIES

Initiate communication during the feasibility and site selection phase – before securing permits. Early outreach builds trust and gives developers insight into local concerns before decisions are finalised.

ENSURE TRANSPARENCY THROUGHOUT THE PROJECT

Provide clear, honest information about safety, environmental impact, timelines, and system limitations. Transparency is critical - especially for a new technology like Airborne Wind Energy where public knowledge is still developing.

ADAPT ENGAGEMENT TO THE LOCAL CONTEXT

Tailor outreach to reflect local identity, land use values, and concerns. Explain the potential advantages of AWE, such as lower noise, minimal visual impact, and a small land footprint, in terms that resonate locally.

OFFER LOCAL BENEFITS

Consider options such as job creation, community investment, or educational partnerships. Demonstrating clear local value can significantly increase acceptance. However, do not overpromise or exaggerate local benefits.

MAINTAIN ONGOING COMMUNICATION AND RESPONSIVENESS

Keep communities informed during construction and operation. Address emerging issues quickly and maintain open, two-way communication channels.